

CONSUMER AWARENESS IN CAGAYAN VALLEY (REGION 2), PHILIPPINES

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Abstract

The study looked into the consumer awareness in Region 2 on their rights and responsibilities and their knowledge of the related provisions in the Consumer Act of the Philippines and other related Trade and Industry Laws. The study used the descriptive-survey method of research. To provide a clear presentation of the data gathered, descriptive statistics were used in describing and understanding the features of specific data through short summaries about the data sample and measures using the frequency, percentages, ranks, average and chi-square. A questionnaire was utilized to generate the responses from the different sectors of the five provinces of the region, namely, Cagayan, Isabela, Batanes, Quirino and Nueva Vizcaya. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the sex and respondents' awareness of advocacy programs in media sources such as local radio. Further, the study showed that there is a significant relationship between the awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs in media sources of information such as national radio, newspapers, and social media when grouped according to the sector. Moreover, it is recommended that there must be a refinement of the DTI information material and improvement of the information dissemination to allow consumers to realize the adverse impact of unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices to their lives.

Keywords: Consumer, Consumer Awareness, Consumer Rights, Consumer responsibilities

Introduction

In any country, the consumers comprise the biggest economic group. It is around them that economic activities revolve. With this, the conceptualization, production, distribution, and marketing of all products have the satisfaction of the consumers as its ultimate target. However, consumer exploitation is rampant. These exploitations which may be unfair trade practices or misbranding are the very things that the consumers must be vigilant of. The question will be - do consumers know that they are being shortchanged or cheated?

Though consumers have considerations before making purchases, many still fall prey of fraudulent trade practices. Engel-Kollat-Blackwell (EKB) Model of Consumer Behavior explains that the consumers make decisions based on factors that influence their assessments through rational insight. EKB outlines a five-stage decision process that consumers go through before purchasing a product or service. It is consisting of five stages: awareness, information processing, evaluation, purchasing decision and outcome analysis.

The awareness stage provides the consumer's opportunity to view and become aware of their desires, needs and interest of a business that they may just discovered and decide to purchase. The information processing stage is when the consumer determines how the products, and the services fulfills their current need and how these products and services

connect or are related to their past experiences and needs. The consumer will then proceed to evaluation stage where he will do his research of the products or services and look if there are better options from competitors.

After product evaluation comes the purchasing decision stage. The consumer will now purchase the product or service that they believe offers the best option. The last stage is the outcome analysis where the customer will assess whether the buying experience is positive or negative. This stage will now determine whether the buyer will be a repeat customer or may return to stage three as they may be dissatisfied.

Awareness of consumers is highlighted in the EKB model for consumer behavior. It is implied then that consumers must be aware of the rights accorded to them by laws. Consumer awareness according to Nedumaran and Mehala (2019) equates to having the knowledge of the different redress mechanisms, laws consumer production, as well as the consumer rights which include the safety from goods and services that the consumer buys, right to health protection and, right to be informed about the quality, price, potency, purity and standard of good, right to choose the best from a variety of others, right to get representation should the situation calls for it, and right to seek redress against any unfair trade practices.

To protect consumers from unfair and fraudulent trade practices, laws have been established. Republic Act No. 7394, or the Consumer Act of the Philippines, protects consumers from trade malpractices, and specifies the rights of consumers and the responsibilities of sellers, producers, retailers, distributors, and manufacturers. The protection of consumers is likewise enshrined in the Philippine 1987 constitution. This year the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), through the Consumer Policy and Advocacy Bureau (CPAB), issued Policy Advisory No. 22-01 on the Eight (8) Basic Consumer Rights. This is to elucidate the legal bases of the rights in guiding consumers on which laws to invoke in reference to their rights.

The Department of Trade and Industry is the government sector that focuses on the strict implementation of the people's rights as consumers. The public's right to basic needs is one of the rights for which DTI has reminded consumers to assert what they are supposed to enjoy. The Eight (8) Basic Consumer Rights are the following: The Right to Basic Needs, The Right to Safety, The Right to Information, The Right to Choose, The Right to Representation, The Right to Redress, The Right to Consumer Education, and The Right to a Healthy Environment.

The right where citizens are given the highest regard to their right for ample food, comfortable clothing, shelter, health care, education and sanitation are fully supported in the guidelines of **Right to basic needs**. This right guarantees adequate and nutritious food, education, clothing, sanitation, shelter, health care, and survival. With this right, consumers expect and look forward to the availability of basic and prime commodities at affordable prices and good quality. On the other hand, the **Right to safety** ensures protection against products or services that are hazardous to health and life. In this right, the consumer should

be protected from the provision of services and marketing of goods that are hazardous to human health and life.

In the Right to Information, the consumer should be protected against misleading or deceptive advertising as well as labeling and has the right to be given the facts and information needed in order to make an informed choice. The **right to information** is defined as 'the **right** to be informed about the quality, quantity, potency, purity, standard and price of goods or services, as the case may be so as to protect the **consumer** against unfair trade practices' in the **Consumer Protection Act** of 1986.

All buyers enjoy the right to look around and closely see among choices of quality products, which are competitive in terms of price, durability, efficiency, and warranty coverage. The **Consumer Bill of Rights** pushed by John F. Kennedy established four basic **rights** - the **right to safety**, the **right** to be informed, and the **right to choose** - the consumer is accorded the right to choose from among various products at competitive prices with an assurance of quality. **Consumer protection** is the duty of the designated arm of the government, government agencies, and various organizations that have established to ensure consumer rights. The right to choose is one basic right for any buyer to be given the opportunity to select the best quality of any commodity he is to purchase without the merchandiser's interfering acts to persuade a buyer to buy another product.

The right of consumers to be heard is exercised in **the right to representation**. This is the right to demonstrate consumer interest in the formulation and implementation of government regulations that would affect the availability of goods and services for consumers. To this, the government imposes to protect its people and represent them in all manners of deceit done by the producers and suppliers. In case of complaints and dissatisfaction on efficiency of purchased goods, **the right to redress** provides for consumers to get an equitable settlement of claims, including payment for misrepresentation, poor quality products, or unsatisfactory services. This right of consumers will give them fair compensation for anything that is procured, which does not comply with the exact description and specifications of the goods being bought.

The basic right of the individual buyer to be informed and educated about the benefits and deficiencies of goods being sold in the market is under his right for consumer education. In this manner, he is also informed of anything hazardous on the quality he is buying. The Right to Consumer Education is the right to obtain knowledge and skills needed so one could be an informed customer. The **right for Consumer education** is the process of preparing a person to be able to choose wisely while making purchases in a culture that values consumption. Typically, it discusses various consumer goods and services, prices, what consumers can anticipate, and accepted business procedures, and anything, which may concern efficiency.

The right to live and work in an environment that is neither dangerous nor threatening and that which allows a life of dignity and well-being is under the eighth consumer right, which is **the right to a healthy environment**. There are commodities considered to be dangerous

so it is just proper to observe safety measures in terms of stacking goods in such areas as free from pollution, away from dangers of fires, erosions, or even toxic elements emitting from stocks. The Right to a Healthy Environment is exercising the right to live and work in an environment which is neither threatening nor dangerous and which permits a life of dignity and well-being.

Consumer **rights** are typically used to refer to a body of law that addresses what manufacturers and suppliers of goods must do to safeguard consumers. These laws were created as a result of numerous court decisions, and they have been influenced by the outcomes of those cases. To know thy rights as consumers is a worldwide issue. The government has assigned the Department of Trade and Industry the task to look closely to the rights of the consumers. The hard work lies wherein consumers should have ample knowledge of the rights they are supposed to exercise. The awareness of rights and responsibilities assures the consumers, and they are protected from Unfair Trading Regulations. They are also protected from unfair practices and ban misleading and aggressive sales tactics. The **Consumer Rights Act** gives everyone the privileges and rights when buying goods and services or digital products. The Department of Trade and Industry is the governing body that implements programs and laws to protect the rights, privileges, and responsibilities of every consumer. The mandates of the Republic under RA 7394 popularly known as the Consumer Act of the Philippines clearly specifies that it shall be the duty of the State to: a) to develop and provide safety and quality standards for consumer products, which includes performance or use-oriented standards, codes of practice and methods of tests; b) to guarantee the public the consistency of standardized products. It is supposed to provide protection to consumers against hazards to health and safety and that of deceptive, unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices.

With DTI at the helm of looking closely into the implementation of the consumer rights, there is a need to assess the awareness of the consumers in the region to see whether the steps and actions employed are effective or not.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to measure the awareness of consumers in Region 2 on their rights and responsibilities and their knowledge of the related provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines and other related Trade and Industry laws.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions, to wit:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondent-consumers in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex
 - 1.2 marital status
 - 1.3 sectoral affiliation
 - 1.4 age
 - 1.5 highest educational attainment
 - 1.6 religious affiliation

- 1.7 family size
- 1.8 family income
2. What is the extent of the consumers' awareness in terms of:
 - 2.1 rights
 - 2.2 responsibilities
 - 2.3 responsible agencies on products and services
 - 2.4 Available remedies for consumer complaints?
3. What are the sources of information of the consumer on the advocacy programs in terms of:
 - 3.1 mass media sources of information on consumer welfare and protection
 - 3.2 interpersonal sources of information on consumer welfare and protection
 - 3.3 Media used in information dissemination on consumer welfare and protection?
4. Are the DTI information materials useful as perceived by the consumers in terms of:
 - 4.1 consumer act
 - 4.2 consumer product guides
 - 4.3 Other related trade and industry laws?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to
 - 5.1 sex
 - 5.2 sectoral affiliation
 - 5.3 number of seminars attended on consumer awareness

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used the descriptive research design to measure the awareness of consumers in Region 2 on their rights and responsibilities and their knowledge of the related provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines and other related Trade and Industry laws. Survey method was used to gather data from the participants to the different provinces in the region.

Participants of the study

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution Participants per Province

Province	Frequency	Percentage
Cagayan	536	33.70
Isabela	712	44.70
Batanes	60	3.80
Quirino	84	5.30
Nueva Vizcaya	200	12.60
Total	1592	100.00

The table shows the distribution of the participants of the survey where the highest frequency belonged to Isabela province and Batanes with the least number of consumer-respondents. Based on the Region 2 Population 2020 Census of Population and Housing, the sample was based on the data given by the Philippine Statistics Authority where among the five provinces comprising Region II, Isabela had the biggest population in 2020 with 1,697,050 persons, followed by Cagayan with 1,268,603 persons, Nueva Vizcaya with 497,432 persons, and Quirino with 203,828 persons. Batanes had the smallest population with 18,831 persons.

Locale of the Study

Cagayan Valley – Region Map

Research Instrument

A questionnaire was utilized to generate the responses from the different sectors of the five provinces of the region, namely, Cagayan, Isabela, Batanes, Quirino and Nueva Vizcaya. A questionnaire was utilized to gather information from the respondents which consisted of two parts: Part 1 was on the profile of the respondents and Part II consisted of the questions pertinent to the study being covered such as their awareness of the different consumer rights and responsibilities and its utilities to remedy certain violations which may be possibly committed by establishments.

Data Gathering Procedure

First, a formal letter was made by the office of the regional director of DTI informing the research group in conducting a survey in the region. Second, the researchers sought permission from the office of the different municipal mayors in the different provinces for the conduct of the survey. Once, the letter approved then the researchers administered the survey questionnaire to the target participants randomly. An interview method was conducted for some sectors like PWDs and senior citizens for some considerations. The survey questionnaires were floated September 2019.

Finally, the questionnaires were retrieved from the target participants right after the survey. The retrieval rate of the survey questionnaire is 100%.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to help describe and understand the features of a particular data through giving short summaries of the sample and measures of the data using the frequency, percentages, ranks, average and chi-square.

Frequency counts, percentages and means were used to analyze the socio-demographic profile of the respondent-consumers.

Ranks and frequency counts were used to assess the extent of the consumers' awareness in terms of rights, responsibilities, responsible agencies on products and services, and available remedies for consumer complaints. Likewise, the awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs ranks was used.

Chi-square test was used to test the significant relationship between the extent of awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to sex, sectoral affiliation and number of seminars attended on consumer awareness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Participants as to age

Age	Frequency	Percent
10-18 years old (youth)	440	27.60
19-59 years old (middle age)	929	58.40
60 years old and above (old)	223	14.00
Total	1592	100.00

Those falling under the 19-59 years old age range account for the biggest number of 929 or 58.40 percent followed by those under 10-18 years old and 223 falls under the age range of 60 years old and above. Conscious preference was given to those whose age ranges from 10-59 years old for it is at these ages where consumer purchasing power is strongest arising out of their current productivity. In the previous study conducted, almost half of the participants (48.9%) were at the age of somewhere between 20 and 39 years. 43.1% of the

participant's age were between 40 and 59 years, and above 60 years was 8%. The participants' average age is 36.9±11.4 years for men and 43.0±13.8 years for females. (Ünsal, G. N., et. al 2010). In addition, Statista (2022), mentioned that from age structure from 2011 – 2021, about 32.28 percent of the total population are aged 0-14, 63.12 are aged 15-64, and the remaining 4.60 percent are 65 years and older. In like manner, the Philippine Statistics Authority (2022) in their survey on age and sex distribution in the Philippine population also showed that of the 108.67 million household population in 2020, a total household population of 33.4 million or 30.70 percent were under 15 years of age, 15 to 64 years totaled to 69.40 million or 63.90 percent while those in age groups 65 years and over composed of the remaining 5.86 million or 5.40 percent.

Table 1.2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	985	61.90
Male	607	38.10
Total	1592	100.00

Table 1.2 presents the distribution of consumer respondents in terms of sex. Female respondents outnumbered males in all provinces. Among 1592 respondents, 985 or 61.90 percent were female and 607 or 38.10 percent were males. In Cagayan, among 536 respondents, 323 or 60.30% were females and 213 or 39.70% were males. In Isabela, among 712 respondents, 445 or 62.50 were females and 267 or 37.50 were males. Furthermore, with 60 respondents, Batanes has 34 or 56.70 females and 26 or 43.30% males. In Quirino, 50 or 59.50 of the 84 respondents were females, while 69 or 34.50 were males. In Nueva Vizcaya, with 200 respondents 131 or 65.50% were females and 69 or 34.50% were males. The flow of the data depicts the world's statistics on the male-female ratio. This finding was supported by Brennan, B. (2009) who asserted that women make up the huge majority of consumers and, in particular, the market for personal care products. Haimovitz, K., & Dweck, C. S. (2017). Further emphasize that a woman who is aware of her rights will instill this mindset in her children, family, and community. As a result, society is strengthened, and women are given the power that may reduce the gender gap at the most fundamental levels of society while raising the level of consumer rights awareness.

Table 1.3 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Marital Status

marital status	Frequency	Percent
Single	854	53.64
Solo Parent	42	2.64
Married	599	37.63
Widowed	89	5.59
Separated	8	0.50
Total	1592	100.0

Table 1.3 shows the distribution of consumer respondents in terms of marital status. Among the 1592 respondents, 854 or 53.64 were single, 599 or 37.63 were married, 89 or 5.59 were widowed/widower, 42 or 2.64 were solo parents and 8 or 0.50 were legally separated. The data based on consumersinternational.org indicates several propositions where the singles' endeavors seek active lifestyles and compensate for the feelings of loneliness that may lead to some marketing activities/implications. Furthermore, in the Philippine Statistics Authority February 2020 report, it stressed that there are 34.8 million singles or unmarried individuals which accounts for 44% of the total population ten years old and above.

Table 1.4 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Highest Educational Attainment

	Frequency	Percent
Elementary Level	114	7.16
Elementary Graduate	495	31.09
High School Level	272	17.09
High School Graduate	104	6.53
Bachelor Level	46	2.89
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	63	3.96
Post-Graduate Level	176	11.06
Completed Graduate Studies	263	16.52
Technical/ Vocational	59	3.71
Total	1592	100.0

In terms of educational level, the consumer respondents may be said to have achieved a fairly high level of educational attainment. Combining those pursuing graduate studies and those who have already completed yielding a total of 439 or 27.60% of the total respondents. However, a combined total of those who have gone through elementary, completed elementary, gone through High School, completed HS and started college is 1031 or 64.80% of the total. Majority of the respondents are those who have not completed college education.

This finding is contradictory to the study conducted by Mittal, I., & Gupta, R. K. (2013) where respondents with high education level and high level of income were more aware as compared to those having poor education level and low-income level. It was surprising to note that even the level of awareness of consumer rights was high but the utilization of these rights was not observed at very good level.

Table 1.5: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Religion

	Frequency	Percent
Roman Catholic	1133	71.17
Baptist	24	1.51
Iglesia Ni Cristo	95	5.97
Jehova's Witnesses	31	1.95
Protestant	35	2.20
Evangelical	11	0.69
Born Again Christian	151	9.48
Islam	6	0.38
JIL Movement	5	0.31
Seventh day Adventist	6	0.38
Others	95	5.97
	1592	100.00

Predominantly a Roman Catholic country, the consumer respondents follow the trend with those coming from this sector of 1,133 or 71.17% of the total. All other religious congregations as INC, Jehovah, etc. make up for the rest of the total. The Philippines proudly boasts to be the only Christian nation in Asia. More than 86 percent of the population is Roman Catholic, 6 percent belong to various nationalized Christian cults, and another 2 percent belong to well over 100 Protestant denominations. In consonance with this finding, Hoh (2018) asserted that the Philippines proudly boast to be the only Christina nation and Asia and that more than 86 percent of the population is Roman Catholic. Roman Catholicism is also the de facto state religion in the Philippines.

Table 1.6 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Sector

	Frequency	Percent
Housewife	147	9.23
Farmers/fisher folks	150	9.42
government employees	208	13.07
Person with Disabilities (PWD)	72	4.52
Business	198	12.44
Students	596	37.44
OSY's/unemployed	69	4.33
Senior citizen	152	9.55
Total	1592	100.00

Table 1.6 shows the distribution of participants in terms of sector. Among the 1592 participants, 596 or 37.40 percent were College/High school students, followed by 208 or 13.10 percent were government/private employees, 198 or 12.40 percent were from the business sector, 152 or 9.50 percent were senior citizens, 150 or 9.40 percent were farmer/fisher folks, 147 or 9.20 percent were housewife, 72 or 4.50 percent were persons

with disability and the least respondents belong to out of school youth/unemployed with 69 respondents or 4.30 percent. The data affirm the population distribution where the greater part is the young adults, particularly the students. This finding is further supported by the study conducted by Makela, CJ & Peters, S (2004) where it presents that students were aware of the consumer issues and that females were more likely to be informed than males. These are topics identified to be taught in consumer education which included consumer rights and responsibilities, purchasing decisions, advertising and others. The delivery methods identified in this endeavor were classes in school, workshops, radio and television programs, and consumer youth clubs. Consumer education programs were found to have an impact on adolescents because most of them were aware of consumer rights and responsibilities and acted as informed consumers on most consumer issues. In the same manner, the United Nations Population Fund presented that 30 million or 28 percent of the Philippine population is young people ranging from ages of 10-24 account for. Age bracket of students in the Philippines for High School (grade 7-12) is 12 to 17 and for College is 18 and above.

Table 1.7 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Family Size

Family size	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 4	419	26.32
4 to 6	935	53.08
More than 7	328	20.60
Total	1592	100.00

The biggest number of families are those with family sizes from 4 to 6 representing almost 55 percent (53.08 percent) of the total and those with less than 4 with 419 or 26.30 percent of the total, one-fifth (20.60 percent) are those coming from families with 7 and up a size. This data is supported by the survey findings of Philippine Statistics Authority and statistica.com in which in the 2008 National Demographic and Health Survey, households in the Philippines consist of an average of 4.8 people. More than one-third (36 percent) of household members are children under the age of 15. More than 80 percent of households are headed by men. Statista Research Department (2022) also found out that in their 2020 population census, the average size of households in the Philippines was 4.1. It is further backed up by Tan, Rosalina. (2021) that the average household has 5 members.

Table 1.7 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Consumer Respondents as to Family Income

Family income	Frequency	Percentage
30,000 and below	1293	81.22
30,001 - 60,000	190	11.93
60,001 - 90,000	61	3.83
90,001 - 120,000	17	1.07
120,001 and above	31	1.95
Total	1592	100.00

Of the total 1592 consumer respondents, 1,293 or 81.22 percent belong to the monthly income bracket of 30,000 and below, most are considered to fall under the low-income group. The rest belong to the 30,000 and above income brackets. This is affirmed in the preliminary data from the Philippine Statistics Authority’s 2021 Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES), the average income of Filipino families in the first half of 2021 was P149, 980 or approximately 25,000 per month. Rosalina Tan (2021) in her study found out that the average monthly household income is PHP 19,444.

2. Awareness on Consumer Rights and Responsibilities

Table 2.1. Awareness on Consumer Rights

	Frequency	Rank
Right to Basic Needs	1315	1 st
Right to Safety	1101	2 nd
Right to Healthy Environment	1048	3 rd
Right to Choice	822	4 th
Right to Information	787	5 th
Right to Consumer Education	761	6 th
Right to Representation	383	7 th
Right to Redress	329	8 th

Table 2.1 indicates the awareness of the respondents on their rights as consumers. It shows that the “Right to Basic Needs” posts the highest with a frequency count of 1,315 out of 1,592 respondents. The right to redress ranks the least to consumers with a frequency of 329 out of 1,592 respondents. The right to basic needs ensures availability of quality basic goods and services to consumers at affordable prices. It includes adequate food, water, clothing, health care, shelter, education, public utilities, and sanitation to lead a decent life (Revilla 2014). Moreover, the result is supported by Abraham Maslow’s theory on the Hierarchy of Needs which suggests that people are motivated to fulfill basic needs before moving on to other more advance needs. On the other hand, the right to redress is the consumers’ right to be compensated for misrepresentation, substandard goods, and unsatisfactory services. The result reveals that respondents have a limited knowledge about this right. This supports the claims of Oishika Banerji (2022) that consumers are sometimes to blame for the goods and services that are offered to them that are improper. They frequently lack complete information about the products or services they are considering. They sometimes accept deliveries of goods or services without regard for their quality. The consumer – respondents should be fully aware and give importance to these rights since this gives consumers the right to request money or other benefits to make up for their loss when they felt cheated due to misrepresentation, shoddy products, or unsatisfactory services.

Table 2.2 Awareness on Consumer Responsibilities

	Frequency	Rank
Environmental Awareness	1224	1
Social Concern	888	2
Critical Awareness	630	3
Action	618	4
Solidarity	435	5

The table shows the extent of the respondents' awareness of their responsibilities as consumers. Environmental awareness ranks no. 1 with 1,224 out of 1,592 respondents while solidarity is least considered with 435 out of 1,592 respondents. This agrees with the study of Citra, 2007 which states that the higher the consumers' environmental awareness, the more the consumers are willing to pay higher prices for eco-friendly products. Consumers should recognize the individual and social responsibility to conserve natural resources and protect the earth for future generations. On the other hand, Solidarity in this context, conception of individual and of solidarity consumption is best understood as an ongoing process of learning, which is influenced by a range of factors that shape individual decision-making in and beyond the market (Valiente-Riedl, 2019). The study reveals that there are more who understand the environmental consequences of consumption. Thus, consumers are expected to segregate their wastes, conserve water and electricity, and lessen the use of products that have negative environmental impacts.

Table 2.3. Consumers' Awareness on the Gov't. Agencies' Assistance on Defective Products and Unsatisfactory Services

Product/Service	Agencies			Percentage*
Senior Citizen Discount	OSCA	LGU	DTI	
	1148	272	98	72.1%
Price of Basic & Prime commodities (i.e. salt, soy sauce, vinegar, sardines, detergent)	DTI	DOH	LGU	
	1252	141	149	78.6%
Meat, Livestock, vegetables, rice, fish	DA	DTI	LGU	
	1105	346	92	69.4%
Airline Promo Fares	DOTC	DTI	CAB	
	878	182	405	55.2%
drugs, cosmetics, medical devices, household products with Hazardous substances	DTI	LGU	DOH/FDA	
	158	91	1271	79.8%
Medical/Hospital Services	DOH	FDA	DTI	
	1413	70	58	88.8%
Labelling & Packaging of manufactured goods and services (processed foods)	DTI	DA	FDA	
	784	110	643	49.2%
False and Misleading Advertisement	DA	DOH	DTI	
	236	164	1093	68.7%
Text Scam	DTI	NTC	DOTC	
	123	1251	132	78.6%

Product Warranty & Services	NTC	DTI	DepED	
	331	1111	68	69.8%
Spa Services (i.e. facial, manicure, pedicure, etc.)	DTI	DOH	LGU	
	519	691	285	43.4%
Labelling and Packaging of drugs, cosmetics and devices	FDA	DTI	BIR	
	964	379	165	60.6%
product quality of electrical products and services	ERC	Consumer Welfare Desk	DTI	
	1091	214	198	68.5%
waste and sewerage-related problems	LWUA	DTI	Consumer Welfare Desk	
	1251	108	160	78.6%
defective product/services (manufactured)	LGU	Consumer Welfare Desk	DTI	
	237	546	718	45.1%
prices of fuel/petroleum products	DOE	DTI	LTFRB	
	888	286	341	55.8%
construction materials	DENR	LGU	DTI	
	793	270	424	49.8%
price tag violation	DA	DTI	DOH	
	157	1304	63	81.9%
telephone, mobile and internet services	DTI	NTC	DOTC	
	111	1229	173	77.2%
deceptive sales acts and practices	Consumer Organization	LGU	DTI	
	679	240	555	42.7%
food(i.e. restaurant, food chains, sidewalk)	FDA	DOH	LGU	
	871	411	223	54.7%
credit card surcharge	BSP	DTI	SEC	
	983	156	350	61.7%
subdivision, Condominiums, Housing	LGU	HLURB	DTI	
	221	1205	73	75.7%
weights and measures (i.e. wet market)	FDA	DTI	LGU	
	411	630	471	39.6%
insurance claims	IC	Consumer Organization	DTI	
	1234	165	99	77.5%
sales promotion (non-food products)	DOH	DTI	DA	
	297	1042	159	65.5%
tuition fees	DEPED/CHE D	LGU	SEC	
	1384	76	48	86.9%
school supplies	DEPED	LGU	DTI	
	974	185	364	61.2%
non-issuance/Fraudulent Official Receipts	BIR	SEC	DTI	
	1224	187	98	76.9%
balikbayan boxes, etc.	DFA	DTI	DOT	
	770	197	526	48.4%
Average				65.4%

The table shows the implementation of consumer benefits and enforcement of price regulations. Majority of the respondents provided correct answers to the question on their

knowledge of the services provided by government agencies to consumers who purchase defective products and avail unsatisfactory services. The Medical/Hospital Services, Telephone, Mobile and Internet Services, and Tuition fees yielded the highest percentages of 88.8%, 81.9% and 86.9%, respectively. This can be attributed to the fact that the majority of the respondents are working in the Government, Business Sector or are College/ High School Students. Thus, they are aware of the functions of these agencies. However, Labelling & Packaging of manufactured goods and services (processed foods), deceptive sales acts and practices, weights, and measures (i.e., wet market), and balikbayan boxes, etc. falls below 50%. This means that more than 50% of the respondents do not know the right agency to approach relative to problems encountered with purchases and availed services.

Table 2.4. Awareness on Remedies Available for Consumer Complaints

	Frequency	Rank
Refund	997	1 st
Replace	764	2 nd
Repair	640	3 rd
Recall	279	4 th

The table shows the respondents' awareness of available remedies for complaints they may have. Refund ranks as the respondents' top remedy and Recall is least subscribed. This is a manifestation that the consumers are aware of RA 7394 that gives the consumers a feeling of security and guarantee that what they are buying is what it is presented to be. If a retailer does not give this guarantee, suspicions will arise prompting the consumers to avoid buying their products again. According to Republic Act 7394 or the Consumer Act of the Philippines, consumers have the right to have any purchased item be returned, exchanged, and refunded if the items are deemed broken or defective. Therefore, it is crucial that customer – respondents must be aware of the return and refund policy.

3. Sources of information of the consumer on advocacy programs

Table 3.1. Mass Media Sources of Information on Consumer Welfare and Protection

	Frequency	Rank
Television	1301	1 st
Radio	1105	2 nd
Internet	977	3 rd
Mobile	743	4 th
Newspapers	682	5 th
Posters	412	6 th
Flyers	381	7 th
Brochures	310	8 th
Telephone hotline	275	9 th
Pamphlets	233	10 th
Cinema	155	11 th

Table 3.1 shows the mass media sources of information on the DTI consumer on advocacy program. Most of the respondents' information on DTI advocacy programs comes from Television, Radio and Internet with 1301, 1105 and 977 respondents, respectively. Cinema, pamphlets and telephone hotlines were the least mass media sources of information on consumer advocacy programs 155, 233 and 275 respondents, respectively.

The findings are in consonance with Sama (2019) that in order to influence customer behavior, marketers put money into a variety of media platforms. The composition of advertisements on each and every media platform is unique, and each one attracts the attention of consumers in a particular way. The impact of TV and the Internet for creating awareness, interest, convictions, purchase, and post-purchase behavior among the consumers is statistically evident. The results also show that magazines and newspapers are effective media in influencing purchase and post-purchase behavior of consumers. The same importance of television was stressed by researchers Mojica, et. al (2016) in their study on UPLB Student' Awareness, Attitude and Practices on Their Consumer Rights and Responsibilities. Generally, the respondent's claim that pieces of information on knowing their rights and responsibilities as consumers are aired on television.

In the advent of fast technology, people have only the button to press to see the latest updates as to information on Consumer Welfare and Protection. To this effect, a great number of respondents have the television as the handiest source of information while being entertained watching the show they follow.

Table 3.2. Interpersonal Sources of Information on Consumer Welfare and Protection

	Frequency	Rank
Friends/Neighbors	795	1
Barangay Captain	760	2
Family Members/ Relatives	738	3
Teacher	567	4
LGU Executives	477	5
School/Universities	473	6
DTI Staff	450	7
Health Workers	437	8
Consumer Organizations	305	9
Market Administrator	264	10
Extension Workers	197	11

Table 3.2 shows the interpersonal sources of information on the DTI consumer on advocacy programs. According to the consumer-respondents, they receive information on the DTI consumer advocacy programs from friends/neighbors with 795, followed by the barangay captains and family members/ relatives with 760 and 738 respondents, respectively. The least interpersonal source of information on consumer advocacy programs comes from

extension workers, market administrators and consumer organizations with 197, 264 and 305 respondents, respectively.

In the study of Mojica et.al. (2016), family and teachers/professors were the preferred medium in learning consumer rights and responsibilities. This clearly shows that the interpersonal sources of information on DTI advocacy programs come from people who have direct contact with the respondents.

Table 3.3. Capacity Building Activities Used in Information Dissemination on Consumer Advocacy Programs

Capacity Building Activities	Frequency	Rank
Seminars/Trainings	1047	1 st
Meetings/ fora	513	2 nd
Public Hearing	474	3 rd
Conferences	446	4 th
Conventions/Summit	349	5 th
Assembly/Congress	340	6 th

Table 3.3 presents the capacity building activities used for information dissemination on the consumer on advocacy programs. It revealed that seminars/trainings and meetings/fora are the top ranked capacity building activities that the respondents received information on consumer advocacy programs with 1047 and 513 respondents, respectively, while assembly/congress and conventions/summit are the least capacity building activities with 349 and 340 respondents, respectively.

As an active move for the department, in pursuance of DTI's commitment to protecting the rights as well as interests of consumers through creation policies and programs which are aimed at sustaining the growth and development of the Philippine economy, the Department of Trade and Industry, Quezon Provincial Office, through the Consumer Protection Division and Negosyo Center Calauag, conducted a seminar on Fair Trade Laws last 21 January 2022, held at the Calauag Livelihood Center. This undertaking ensured to oversee the effective implementation and enforcement of trade regulation and fair-trade laws. In relation to other forms of information dissemination, the Rural Health Information Hub have id Rodrigo and Andres (2019) in their paper have stressed that public consultation is one of the key regulatory tools in improving transparency, efficiency and effectiveness of regulation alongside Regulatory Impact Analysis (RIA), regulatory alternatives and improved accountability arrangements.

All the identified use of media to disseminate information as a way to make consumers aware of their rights, obligations, and privileges are useful avenues to let the public know that the programs of the government are all crafted for the benefits and welfare of everyone.

4. Usefulness of DTI information materials as perceived by the consumers

Table 4.1. The usefulness of the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) information materials

(Consumer Act) as perceived by the consumers

Consumer Act Provision	Usefulness			
	Useful	Percentage	Not Useful	Percentage
Advertising and sales promotion	922	57.9	233	14.6
Product and service warranties	757	47.6	292	18.3
Product quality and safety	718	45.1	310	19.5
Price tag law	668	42.0	326	20.5
Labeling and fair packaging	610	38.3	344	21.6
No return, no exchange	571	35.9	424	26.6
Service and repair shops	535	33.6	384	24.1
Liability for product and services	468	29.4	423	26.6
Deceptive sales acts and practice	444	27.9	430	27.0
False, deceptive, and misleading advertisement	375	23.6	481	30.2
Prohibiting chain distribution plans or pyramid sales	363	22.8	473	29.7
Unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices	315	19.8	510	32.0
Average	562	35.3	386	24.2

Table 4.1 presents the perception of the consumer-respondents on the usefulness of the Department of Trade and Industry information materials on the provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines of 1991. It shows that an average of 562 or 35.3% of the participants perceive that information materials on the provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines of 1991 are useful while an average of 386 or 24.2% perceive it as not useful. It also reveals that 922 or 57.9% of the consumer respondents recognize that information material on advertising and sales promotion is the most useful. However, 501 or 32% of the consumer respondents identify information materials on unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices as the least useful.

The findings reflect how consumers think about the information materials developed by the DTI relative to the provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines of 1991 and how it contributes to the awareness of the consumers on their rights and responsibilities. Generally, it indicates that the information materials developed are inadequate and need refinement to meet the expectations of the consumers. It also denotes that the consumers are aware of the advertising and sales promotion provisions. Furthermore, it can be argued that they are least aware of the unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices provisions. The study of Makela and Peters (2004) supported these findings when they argued that consumer education teaching is refined by including consumer rights and responsibilities, purchasing decisions, advertising, and others.

Table 4.2 the usefulness of the DTI information materials (Customer Product Guides) as perceived by the consumers

Consumer Product Guides	Useful			
	Useful	Percentage	Not Useful	Percentage
Standards on Home Appliances	726	45.6%	288	18.1%
PS and ICC Mark	657	41.3%	370	23.2%
Standards on Electrical and Writing Devices	633	39.8%	337	21.2%
Standards on Christmas Lights	630	39.6%	329	20.7%
Standards on Cement	520	32.7%	393	24.7%
Standards on LPG Cylinders	510	32.0%	403	25.3%
Standards on Automotive Battery	439	27.6%	427	26.8%
Standards on Plywood	423	26.6%	447	28.1%
Standards on Steel Bars	417	26.2%	461	29.0%
Standards on Equal-Leg Angle Bars	376	23.6%	468	29.4%
Average	533	33.5%	392	24.6%

The table shows the usefulness of the DTI information materials to the consumers in Region 02. It shows that an average of 533 or 33.5% of the participants perceive that DTI information materials on customer product guides are useful while an average of 392 or 24.6% perceive it as not useful. Of the 1,592, 726 or 45.6% of the respondents considered “Standards on Home Appliances” useful in contrast to the 288 or 18.1% who consider them not useful. This is a manifestation that consumers consider their protection against many types of hazards such as electrical, mechanical, thermal, fire, and radiation with standards, on home appliances. In like manner, “PS and ICC Mark” is also useful with 657 or 41.3%, while 370 or 23.2% find it not useful. As stated in the Standards and Conformance Portal of the Bureau of Philippine Standards, DTI, the Philippine Standard (PS) Quality as well as the Safety Mark, and Import Commodity Clearance (ICC) Sticker serve as the consumers’ guide and guarantee of a safe product purchase as they are certified of quality conforming to the relevant Philippine National Standards (PNS). The products covered by the Bureau of Philippine Standards (BPS) Mandatory Product Certification Schemes, both locally manufactured and imported, are required to bear the PS mark or ICC sticker before they are distributed in the Philippine Market. On the other hand, 417 or 26.2% of the respondents find the consumer product guide on “Standards on Steel Bars” important and 461 or 29.0% find it not important. Although the Department of Trade and Industry’s Bureau of Philippine Standards (DTI-BPS) approves the Philippine National Standard (PNS) 49:2020 Steel bars of concrete reinforcement – specification, several consumers find it not useful. This is because the first thing Filipinos consider in choosing the construction material/s to use is the cost. The least useful to 376 or 23.6% of consumers are the “Standards on Equal-Leg Angle Bars”. Since standards are correlated with price, the insufficiency of the consumers’ income made them choose products with a more affordable alternative.

Table 4.3: The usefulness of the DTI information materials (Other relevant trade and industry laws) as perceived by the consumers

Other Relevant Trade and Industry Laws	Usefulness			
	Useful	Percentage	Not Useful	Percentage
Senior Citizen Discount	870	54.6%	240	15.1%
Price Act/Basic Needs and Prime Commodities	797	50.1%	276	17.3%
PWD Discounts	746	46.9%	275	17.3%
Business Name Law (as amended)	490	30.8%	401	25.2%
Tobacco Regulations Act	460	28.9%	424	26.6%
Freight Forwarding (Balikbayan Boxes)	440	27.6%	421	26.4%
Gift Check Policy	412	25.9%	443	27.8%
No-Short Changing Act	368	23.1%	449	28.2%
Repair Shop Accreditation	367	23.1%	463	29.1%
Average	550	34.5%	377	23.7%

Table 4.3 shows the perception of the consumer respondents on the usefulness of the DTI information materials on other relevant trade and industry laws. It reveals that an average of 550 or 34.5% of the consumer respondents perceive that the information materials are useful while an average of 377 or 23.7% of the consumer respondents perceive it as not useful. It also discloses that 870 or 54.6% of them recognize that information materials developed on Senior Citizen Discount are useful. Furthermore, it divulges that 463 or 29.1% of the consumers identify information materials on repair shop accreditation law are not useful.

The findings represent how consumers view the DTI's information materials relative to the other relevant trade and industry laws, as well as how it helps the consumers understand their rights and obligations. It demonstrates that the consumers are most aware of the provisions on senior citizen discounts. On the other hand, it may be claimed that they are the least aware of the provisions of repair shop accreditation.

5. Relationship between the consumer's awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information and the selected variables

Table 5.1. Test of significant relationship on the awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according sex

Categories	Chi Square Value	Df	p-value	Decision
National Radio	4.527	2	0.104	NS
Local radio	12.674	2	0.002**	Significant
Television	6.706	2	0.152	NS
Newspaper	3.437	2	0.179	NS
Social Media	1.908	4	0.895	NS

**significant at 0.01 level

Table 5.1 illustrates the significant relationship test on the consumer awareness of advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to sex. The computed p-value <0.05 level of significance under local radio means that there is a significant relationship between the sex and respondents' awareness of advocacy programs in media

sources such as local radio. This result is keeping with Haji & Stock (2021). They said that differences in sex can affect the approaches and decision-making of consumers saying further that responses of males and females to advertising marketing differ. Based on the cross-tabulations, the female group is more likely not aware compared to the male group on advocacy programs in media sources of information as to local radio. Emami & Naderi (2018); Pinar et al., (2017) have the same findings. They found out that males and females have different paths in data processing and in evaluating their services. Females are more likely than males to have negative evaluations of services since females consider more value to negative information. Other profiles such as national radio, television, newspaper, and social media found no significant relationship on the consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to sex since the p-values > 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5.2. Test of significant relationship on the consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according sector

Categories	Chi Square Value	Df	p-value	Decision
National Radio	35.089	7	0.000**	Significant
Local radio	10.145	7	0.181	NS
Television	18.314	14	0.193	NS
Newspaper	49.375	7	0.000**	Significant
Social Media	193.004	14	0.000**	Significant

**significant at 0.01 level

Table 5.2 shows the test of significant relationship of consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to sector namely housewives, farmers, government employees, persons with disability, business sector, college/high school students, unemployed and senior citizens. The table shows a significant relationship between the awareness of the consumer on advocacy programs in media sources of information such as national radio, newspapers, and social media when grouped according to the sector. As to national radio, government employees as well as the college and high school students are more likely not aware than the rest of the sector consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information. On the other hand, under social media, government employees as well as the college and high school students are more likely aware of the consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information. In terms of newspapers, the business sector and college/high school students are more likely not aware than the rest of the sector on consumers' awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information. This may result in businesses not being able to comply with the advocacy programs and rules of DTI at the same time may result in students not knowing whether or not they are enjoying or are being denied their rights as customers.

No significant relationship was found between local radio and television on consumers' awareness of advocacy programs in media sources of information. The above finding is supported by the claim of Statistica.com that approximately 86% of the age group of 18 to

24 is internet users in the Philippines, and such gradually decreases as the age level increases. Further, Philippine Statistics Authority also is in agreement with this as it detailed that in 2019, Filipinos 10 to 64 years old typically watched television (96.0%), and listened to radio (75.2%). Typically, Filipinos 10 to 30-years old who were enrolled in school in 2019 watched television (97.2%), read a magazine (88.8%) and surfed the internet for social media (86.8%). Writing a report/correspondence (62.7%), attending meetings (61.9%), and reading a newspaper (59.7%) were the least mass media exposure they do. This is in support of the results of PSA’s 2019 Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS), where it is said that Filipinos 10 to 64-years old who are exposed to different forms of mass media registered high functional literacy rates in 2019. Researchers Madden (2010) and Lenhart et al, (2010) arrived at the same findings. Madden (2010) states that across the United States, the use of social media varies greatly by age with older generations participating less often than younger ones. Of the social media users with ages 18-29, 86% have active engagement in social networking sites compared to 61% of users in the 30-49 year old category, 47% of users 50-64 year old bracket, and 26% only of users over 65 years of age (Madden, 2010). To Lenhart, et al. (2010), younger generations are still the greatest users of social media.

Table 5.3. Test of significant relationship on the consumers’ awareness on advocacy programs in media sources of information, when grouped according to trainings and seminar attended

Categories	Chi Square Value	df	p-value	Decision
National Radio	40.73	2	0.000	Significant
Local radio	10.382	2	0.001	Significant
Television	43.163	2	0.000	Significant
Newspaper	43.009	2	0.000	Significant
Social Media	57.367	2	0.000	Significant

**significant at 0.01 level

Table 3 explains the significant relationship test on the consumers’ awareness of advocacy programs in media sources of information when grouped according to trainings and seminars on consumer awareness attended.

The p-values<0.05 level of significance means that there is a significant relationship in all sources of information on the consumers’ awareness of advocacy programs when grouped according to trainings and seminars attended. This proves that DTI awareness seminars and trainings conducted are serving their purpose of providing the necessary information for customers.

Training and seminars are other modes of transferring information and providing awareness to consumers. Variables, source of information, consumer awareness, and training and seminars attended has a significant relationship.

In the study conducted by Mojica, et al., (2016), they said that consumer education has been viewed as a vehicle to provide information in helping consumers make better choices of goods and services in the marketplace.

Their findings showed that the source of awareness of consumer rights and responsibilities comes primarily from, TV, printed materials, radio, government websites, social networking sites, books, and seminars. Backing the above data, Ishak and Zabil (2012); Yilmaz and Kocuglu (2017), stated that education (training and seminar) has a significant relationship with consumer awareness and conscious consumption.

Summary of Findings

A. Socio-demographic profile

1. Majority (58.40%) of the participant's ages 19-59 years old for it is at these ages where consumer purchasing power is strongest arising out of their current productivity.
2. Majority (61.90%) of the participants are female.
3. Majority (53.64%) of the participants are single.
4. Majority (31.09%) of the participants are elementary graduate.
5. Majority (71.17%) of the participants are dominant Roman Catholic.
6. As to sector, the majority (37.44%) of them are students.
7. The biggest number of families are those with family sizes from 4 to 6 representing almost 55 percent (53.08 percent) of the total population.
8. As to monthly family income, most (81.22%) of the participants fall under low income earner with an income of below 30,000.

B. Extent of the consumer's awareness

1. The overall level of awareness recorded an average composite score of 43.9% level of awareness Deprived from the two dimensions, i.e. Awareness of consumer rights and responsibilities and on DTI's Consumer Awareness Programs, the former was given 51.65% and the latter, 36.2% yielding the composite score cited beforehand.
2. As regards their rights, highest was given to "Right to Basic Needs" and the least "Right to Redress".
3. On their responsibilities, highest was given to "Environmental Awareness".
4. The overall impression given by data collected shows the correct identification of agencies responsible on products and services like in the senior citizen discount by OSCA, drugs, cosmetics, etc. Caution should be taken in interpreting the data considering a good number of wrong identification in some areas.

5. Consumers are not aware of “refund” as remedy available for consumer complaint and “recall” as least.
- C. Sources of information of the consumer on the advocacy programs
1. Most popular media medium for the dissemination of consumer welfare and protection program is TV and the least is cinema.
 2. Most common source of consumer welfare and protection are friends or neighbors and the least is extension workers.
 3. Most common medium of information dissemination are seminars/trainings and least on holding of assembly/congress
 4. Majority (74.1%) use consumer information materials. The most commonly used DTI information materials are advertising and sales promotion and the least is on unfair and unconscionable sales act and practice.
 5. Majority (57.9%) consider DTI information materials useful.
 6. Most popular consumer product guides used are “standards on home appliances” (45.6%) and the PS and ICC mark (41.3%).

CONCLUSION

The consumer awareness assessment survey in Cagayan Valley was conceptualized and implemented to measure the awareness of consumers on their rights and responsibilities and their knowledge of the related provisions of the Consumer Act of the Philippines and other related Trade and Industry laws.

The result of the survey is expected to serve as basis in coming up with programs and the projects that would increase consumer awareness and vigilance resulting to enhanced consumer protection.

The findings of the study shows that the consumers’ awareness of their rights provides opportunity of creating more responsible business environment as it can also improve the consumer protection legislation effectiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

This study on Consumer Awareness in Region 2 has the following recommendations. First, the maximized utilization of mass media such as internet, mobile, television and radio as the source of information on consumer welfare and protection act be considered. LGUs, other government agencies and schools/universities must likewise utilize other interpersonal sources of information on consumer welfare and protection act. Dissemination of information on Consumer Welfare and Protection in the academe must also be taken into account.

Furthermore, there must be a refinement of the DTI information materials and improvement of the information dissemination to allow consumers to realize the adverse impact of unfair and unconscionable sales acts and practices to their lives. Moreover, business sectors need to provide accurate, unbiased information about the standards on equal-leg angle bars they offer and the services they provide.

Further, the information materials on repair shops' accreditation must include the benefits of subjecting the repair shops for accreditation to ensure quality services. Lastly, research on the impact of this study to the consumers should be conducted for the improvement of DTI's programs and initiatives.

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